

manure, and 1 part sand. About 10 days before heading, one set of materials was transferred to a glasshouse chamber where temperature was maintained at 18°C. The other set was grown under normal temperature (30°C). Days to flower; effective tillers per hill; yield per hill; panicle weight, length, and exertion; spikelet fertility; pollen fertility; crude protein and amylose, and gelatinization temperature in cold stress and normal conditions were recorded. Cold injury was calculated as the difference between normal and stress conditions, expressed as a percentage of the norm.

Analysis of combining ability showed the importance of additive and dominance gene action to cold tolerance inheritance for all indices studied. Dominance effects were stronger for all characters except panicle weight and spikelet fertility. Var-

iance component analysis yielded similar results.

Proportional values among genetic components suggested there are more dominant than recessive genes. Panicle exertion and pollen fertility had asymmetrical dominant and recessive gene distributions in the parents. Symmetrical distribution was observed for the remaining indices. Positive and negative alleles at loci showing dominance were asymmetrically distributed in the parents for all cold tolerance characters studied. Combining ability analysis and genetic component analysis showed overdominance for all indices except panicle weight and spikelet fertility and pollen fertility.

IR3941-45-Plp 2B, Himdhan, IR2637-44-2, and IR30 were the best general combiners for cold tolerance (see table). Cross-

ses of IR3941-45-Plp 2B with Zenith and IR30; IR579 with Himdhan; and IR2637-44-2 with Zenith were the most promising for incorporating cold tolerance. They represented all possible combinations between parents of high, average, and low general combining ability (gca). Of these crosses, IR3941-45-Plp 2B/IR30 involved both parents with high gca and can be exploited through recurrent selection. □

ERRATUM

S. S. Malik. Gamma ray-induced semi-dwarf mutants in Basmati 370. *IRRN 7 (6) (Dec 1982), page 4*: In the column *Scnt* in the table, *No* should be changed to *Yes*.

Pest management and control DISEASES

Purification and properties of grassy stunt-associated filamentous particles

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Filamentous (6-8 nm diameter) and isometric (18-20 nm diameter) virus-like particles were found in a partially purified fraction of rice grassy stunt (GSV) infected rice plants. Filamentous particles were numerous in the fraction and isometric particles were scarce.

Filamentous particles were purified by clarification with Mg-bentonite and CCl₄, PEG treatment, and sucrose density-gradient centrifugation. Electron microscopy of the purified fraction revealed numerous filamentous particles and a few contaminants (see figure). Some filaments were circular and 200-2,400 nm long. Length distribution peaked at 1,000-1,300 nm. The UV absorption spectrum of the purified fraction was typical of a nucleoprotein

— maximum absorbance 260 nm, minimum absorbance 247 nm, and 260/280 ratio was 1.28 ± 0.3 . Filamentous particles had RNA and single coat protein of 31,000 daltons.

Antiserum was obtained by injecting rabbits with the purified filamentous particles. In the precipitin ring interface test, titer against purified filaments was 1:1280. A filamentous antigen was detected in RGS-infected leaf and RGS-exposed brown planthopper extracts diluted 1/4096 and 1/1024, respectively, by a latex agglutination test using the antiserum. The antiserum did not react

with planthopper and virus-free leaf extracts.

Purified filamentous particles were injected into the abdomen of second-instar nymphs of the brown planthopper to test infectivity of the particles. None of the injected brown planthoppers became infective.

Specific reaction between the antiserum and extracts of GSV-infected leaves and exposed insect vectors suggests that the nucleoprotein may cause GSV. Relations between the nucleoprotein and isometric particles remain to be clarified.

Electron micrograph of purified filamentous particles—X 150,000